

The Independent Scientific Advisor programme

Helping small businesses to unlock AI

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BridgeAI

BridgeAI is helping small businesses to unlock AI

BridgeAI's ISAs offer vital guidance to support smaller businesses on their AI adoption journeys, and can connect them with relevant experts and communities. With targeted specialist support at the right time, challenges can be overcome.

Idea generation and exploration

Architectural firm Orms has been working with ISA Dr Andy Corbett to investigate how AI adoption can make the company's internal processes more efficient – and to identify the right tools for the job, including generative AI software such as ChatGPT and Midjourney.

“We knew there were likely to be aspects of our workflow that could be made more efficient with AI. Our conversations with Andy have given us the confidence to start using out-of-the-box AI in a number of day-to-day tasks, freeing up time for other aspects of the job.”

Rachel Hoolahan
Associate Director, Orms

Specialist technical support

AI adoption requires specialised technical expertise that small and medium enterprises often don't have. Gpeto AI is developing AI algorithms to help pre-validate and assess planning applications, making life easier for the applicant and the local authority. Their team is working with ISA Dr Andy Corbett on training a computer vision model to assess architectural drawings, including the differences between current and proposed plans.

“Andy's technical support on our algorithm development has been very valuable. Being part of a programme like BridgeAI is great for startups with limited resources and definitely gives you a better chance of success.”

Harold Cabrera
CEO, Gpeto AI

Recruiting the right talent

Finding the right talent is critical for small and medium enterprises looking to bring AI expertise in-house, but recruitment can be challenging when it's in a new or technical field. When a consultancy supporting social housing providers in their decarbonisation efforts wanted to recruit a Senior Data Engineer, ISA Dr Andy Corbett was able to help.

“The meetings I've had with Andy about recruitment have been really beneficial – particularly as I don't have a technical background myself. We've discussed what we need from this important new role in terms of skills and in the context of what we're aiming to do with data and AI.”

Anonymised participant

Networking and opportunities

Making the right connections can drive success in AI adoption, whether meeting potential collaborators or hearing about opportunities to access funding and support. BridgeAI matched AI adopter PorthouseDean, which provides structural calculations for building projects, with ISA Dr Rachael Stickland. Rachael has helped them to engage with relevant support networks for valuable insights and opportunities.

“Rachael has helped us engage with the broader ecosystem of support that exists across the UK through organisations such as Innovate UK, as well as The Turing's own activities.”

Dr Guy Marshall

Chief Technology Officer, PorthouseDean

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